

Fast, Low-resource, Accurate, Robust, and Effectual Medical Image Segmentation and Classification in 3D CT and MRI Scans: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Fast, Low-resource, Accurate, Robust, and Effectual Medical Image Segmentation and Classification in 3D CT and MRI Scans

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

FLARE 2026

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Medical imaging plays a central role in disease diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment planning. Although deep learning has substantially advanced medical image analysis, developing general-purpose models that are fast, resourceefficient, accurate, and robust across diverse clinical scenarios remains a major challenge. Addressing these limitations is crucial for improving global healthcare delivery, particularly in resourceconstrained environments. To this end, we have organized a series of community-driven FLARE challenges aimed at accelerating progress in generalizable medical image segmentation.

Since 2021, the FLARE challenges have progressively expanded in clinical scope, data scale, and technical complexity:

FLARE 2021: segmentation of 4 abdominal organs in 511 CT scans

FLARE 2022: segmentation of 13 abdominal organs in 2,300 CT scans

FLARE 2023: segmentation of 13 abdominal organs and pan-cancer lesions in 4,500 CT scans

FLARE 2024: pan-cancer segmentation, laptopbased CT organ segmentation, and unsupervised domain adaptation for MRI, using 10,000+ CT and 4,000+ MRI scans

FLARE 2025: pan-cancer segmentation, laptopbased CT organ segmentation, unsupervised domain adaptation for MRI and PET, and development of foundation and multimodal models using 10,000+ CT and 10,000+ MRI scans

Leading algorithms from these challenges can now segment 13 organs and multiple abdominal lesion types within 10 seconds on full-resolution 3D CT volumes containing over one million voxels. These advances significantly improve segmentation accuracy, computational efficiency, and cross-domain generalization. Building on this trajectory, FLARE 2026 aims to address critical clinical needs and emerging challenges in developing foundation-level and multimodal AI systems for medical imaging. The challenge focuses on three subtasks:

- Pan-cancer segmentation: develop robust lesion segmentation across multiple disease types in CT scans.
- Self-configured multi-task learning: develop self-configuring models capable of joint 3D medical image segmentation and classification that adapt automatically to diverse datasets.
- Multimodal medical image parsing: generalist vision-language models that support classification, detection, counting, measurement, and regression across multiple imaging modalities.

The anticipated impact of FLARE 2026 is to catalyze innovations in resource-efficient, generalizable, and multimodal AI systems, establishing new performance benchmarks in medical image analysis. Clinically, advancements from this challenge will directly enhance patient care by enabling accurate, reliable, and widely accessible imaging solutions, helping bridge diagnostic disparities between high-resource and low-resource healthcare environments.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Medical Image Analysis, Segmentation, Multi-modal model, Diagnosis

Year

2026

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

1. Pan-cancer segmentation: Large-scale benchmark designed for cross-disease lesion generalization rather than single-organ or single-tumor segmentation. Models must detect and segment heterogeneous cancers that vary widely in location, morphology, attenuation, and size, enabling evaluation of true pan-cancer capability.
2. Self-configured multi-task learning: this task unifies segmentation and classification into a single joint-learning framework and introduces a new paradigm by shifting from manually engineered pipelines to self-configured, fully automated model design systems. Instead of requiring human experts to determine architecture choices, patch sizes, normalization strategies, and loss balancing for each dataset, this task challenges participants to build models that can autonomously infer optimal configurations based on the data itself.
3. Multimodal model for medical image parsing: The integration of multimodal images into a unified analysis framework represents a frontier in medical imaging. This task challenges participants to develop vision-language models capable of handling different modalities and tasks, addressing a significant gap in current AI methods that typically focus on single modalities.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

Task 1 supports clinical workflows that require fast and consistent wholebody tumor analysis. Application scenarios include oncology staging, treatment response monitoring, tumor burden quantification, and largescale population studies where fully manual segmentation is infeasible. Automated pancancer segmentation also benefits radiotherapy planning, metastasis screening, and Aassistant clinical reporting by providing precise lesion maps across diverse cancer types.

Task 2 targets scenarios where medical institutions acquire heterogeneous 3D imaging data and lack the resources to customdesign models for each task. It enables plugandplay AI systems for organspecific and wholebody segmentation, tumor subtype classification, automated triage, and general 3D diagnostic support. Hospitals, research labs, and multicenter trials can benefit from models that selfconfigure to new scanners, protocols, and anatomical regions without manual engineering, supporting scalable deployment across sites.

Task 3 aims at building generalist models that can support diverse clinical workflows across departments with a single unified system. Application scenarios include crossmodality diagnosis, lesion detection, cell or gland counting, anatomical measurement, and continuous outcome prediction. Such models are particularly valuable for integrated health systems, pointofcare diagnostics, and large hospitals seeking to reduce the cost of maintaining multiple taskspecific AI tools.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

This challenge has three subtasks, which need a longer time for top teams to present their solutions.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

30-50. We had 30-50 successful docker submissions in the past FLARE challenges. Thus, we expect a similar number in FLARE 2026.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Yes

MICCAI LNCS proceedings

Indicate if you want to offer MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings to the participants. Publishing a proceedings volume is optional and at the discretion of each challenge's organizers. At a minimum, organizers must ensure that a description of each participant's submission is publicly available. Organizers who wish to publish MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings must adhere to the MICCAI Satellite events publication process.

Yes

Collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR)

In collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR), we announce special clinical interest topics with associated clinicians who can help with the preparation of the proposals; the best 3 challenge proposals on these topics will get the opportunity to present their challenges at the European Congress of Radiology (ECR) 2027 in a special session. If you want to organize a challenge in collaboration with ESR on one of these topics, please reach out to the MICCAI Challenges Team (miccai-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de) and we will put you in contact with the corresponding clinician.

Challenge in collaboration with ESR. Ticking 'Yes' implies that the challenge has been prepared in collaboration with the clinical contact point.

No

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

We plan to organize an on-site challenge and only need basic equipment: projectors, computers, monitors, loud speakers, and microphones.

TASK 1: Task 1: Pan-Cancer Segmentation in CT scans

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Deep learning has emerged as the predominant method for cancer segmentation in CT scans. However, most existing models are designed and trained for specific cancer types, limiting their generalizability and scalability. With the rising prevalence of various cancers and the increasing demand for personalized medicine, there is a critical need for a universally applicable, resource-efficient, and highly accurate pan-cancer segmentation method.

In MICCAL FLARE 2025, we introduced the pan-cancer segmentation challenge on whole-body CT scans, pushing the boundaries of cancer segmentation research. The winning solution achieved DSC and NSD scores of 0.43 and 0.46, respectively, indicating significant room for improvement. This has inspired us to continue organizing this challenge to drive further advancements in pan-cancer segmentation.

Our challenge task has three main features:

- Task: whole-body cancer segmentation (automatic and promptable), across diverse cancer types.
- Dataset: 15,600 CT scans (15,000/100/500 for training/validation/testing), covering whole-body cancer types
- Evaluation Metrics: segmentation accuracy (DSC, NSD) and segmentation efficiency (runtime and GPU consumption)

Compared to FLARE 2025, we have increased an additional 10,000 synthetic CT scans with tumor annotations for model development, aiming to empower participants to build more robust and accurate models, ultimately advancing the state of the art in pan-cancer segmentation.

Clinical value: This task addresses the critical need for universally applicable segmentation methods that can handle heterogeneous cancers varying in location, morphology, and size. The models can support workflows requiring rapid, whole-body tumor analysis, such as oncology staging and treatment response monitoring.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Segmentation, Pan-cancer, Foundation Model, Synthetic data augmentation

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Jun Ma (University Health Network, Vector Institute)

Sumin Kim (University of Toronto, University Health Network, Vector Institute)

Jian He (Nanjing Drum Tower Hospital)

Bo Wang (University of Toronto, University Health Network, Vector Institute)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Jun Ma (junma.ma@mail.utoronto.ca)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Define the clinical tasks and metrics, and verify data quality

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

CodaBench (Similar to the MICCAI FLARE 2023-2025 Challenge)

Each task will have an independent challenge platform.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

N/A

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Participants should develop fully automatic models. User interaction is allowed for curating training data (i.e. excluding some training samples).

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Only the provided challenge data is allowed to be used but publicly available pre-trained models are allowed to be used.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

We will provide certificates and souvenirs for the top-5 teams.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All results will be announced publicly.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

All participants have the opportunity to publish their methods on LNCS proceedings.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker containers

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

We will provide a validation set for participants to pre-evaluate their algorithms. The testing set has the same format as the validation set. To avoid overfitting the testing set, we only offer one submission opportunity on the testing set.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

1 April 2026 (12:00 AM EST): Launch challenge registration and release training and validation data.

15 April 2026 (12:00 AM EST): Release validation dataset and open validation submission.

1 September 2026 (12:00 AM EST): Deadline for the testing submission.

15 September 2026 (12:00 AM EST): Invite top teams to prepare presentations and participate in the MICCAI 2026 Satellite Event.

4/8 October 2026: Announce final results.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Our dataset was curated from public domains (CC-BY-NC) and global data contributors with REB permits. There is no patient information included. Thus, we do not need additional ethics approval.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Evaluation code will be made available with the training data.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Top 5 teams should make their code publicly available. The remaining teams are encouraged to make their code publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Only the organizers have access to the test case labels. We are currently looking into which companies are willing to sponsor the challenge in the form of awards and computational resources.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort will be patients with disease cancer types where the images were acquired in different centers with different manufacturers.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort is composed of patients with over 15 cancer types, such as lung cancer, liver cancer, kidney cancer, pancreas cancer, and so on, which were curated from 50+ different medical centers.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Computed Tomography

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The 3D image data will be released as compressed Nifti1Image.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No additional information regarding each patient will be released.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The dataset covers whole-body regions, including head, chest, abdomen, and pelvis

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Participants have to submit a Docker image that can segment various lesions in CT scans.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Hardware requirements, Runtime, Robustness

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The dataset was acquired from various manufacturers, such as Siemens, GE, Philips, Toshiba, Imatron, Vital, and PHMS.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Our dataset is adapted from TCIA, MSD, KiTS, autoPET, and data contributors from collaborators and local hospitals under the license permission. Thus, the acquisition protocols are very diverse. Detailed Information can be found in the following references.

[1] Simpson A, et al. A Large Annotated Medical Image Dataset for the Development and Evaluation of Segmentation Algorithms. ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:1902.09063.

- [2] Heller N, et al. The kits19 challenge data: 300 kidney tumor cases with clinical context, ct semantic segmentations, and surgical outcomes. arXiv preprint arXiv:1904.00445 (2019).
- [3] Clark K, et al. The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA): maintaining and operating a public information repository. *Journal of Digital Imaging* 26, no. 6 (2013)
- [4] Ma J, et al. Abdomenct-1k: Is abdominal organ segmentation a solved problem. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* (2021).
- [5] Grossberg A, et al. Imaging and Clinical Data Archive for Head and Neck Squamous Cell Carcinoma Patients Treated with Radiotherapy. *Scientific Data* 5:180173 (2018)
- [6] Fedorov A, et al. DICOM reencoding of volumetrically annotated Lung Imaging Database Consortium (LIDC) nodules. *Medical Physics* (2020)
- [7] Ma. J, et al. Unleashing the strengths of unlabelled data in deep learning-assisted pan-cancer abdominal organ quantification: the FLARE22 challenge. *The Lancet Digital Health* 6.11 (2024): e815-e826.
- [8] Ma. J, et al. Automatic organ and pan-cancer segmentation in abdomen ct: the flare 2023 challenge. *ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:2408.12534*
- [9] Ma. J, et al. Efficient MedSAMs: Segment Anything in Medical Images on Laptop. *ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:2412.16085*
- c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.
- Alberta Health Services
Barretos Cancer Hospital, Barretos, Sao Paulo, Brazil
Beaumont Health System, Royal Oak, MI
BioPartners, CA
Boston Medical Center, Boston, MA
Brigham and Women's Hospital, Boston, MA
Cleveland Clinic
Cureline, Inc. team and clinical network, Brisbane, CA
Hebrew University of Jerusalem
International Institute for Molecular Oncology, Poznan
IRCAD Institute Strasbourg
Lahey Hospital & Medical Center, Burlington, MA
Ludwig Maxmilian University of Munich
M Health Fairview
M.D. Anderson Cancer Center, Houston TX
Mayo Clinic, Rochester, MN

Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center (New York, NY, USA)

National Cancer Institute, Bethesda, MD

National Institutes of Health, Bethesda MD

Polytechnique & CHUM Research Center Montreal

Radboud University Medical Center of Nijmegen

Roswell Park Cancer Institute, Buffalo NY

Sheba Medical Center

St. Joseph's Hospital and Medical Center, Phoenix, AZ

Tel Aviv University

The National Institutes of Health Clinical Center(NIH)

University of California, San Francisco, CA

University of Chicago

University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, NC

University of Pittsburgh/UPMC, Pittsburgh, PA

University of Sheffield

University of Southern California

Washington University School of Medicine, St. Louis, MO

Cancer Center West China Hospital

Erasmus MC Cancer Institute, Rotterdam

Fudan University Shanghai Cancer Center

Longgang Central Hospital of Shenzhen, China

Longgang District People's Hospital

University Hospital Basel

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data annotation is overseen by the challenge clinical chair Dr. Jian He, who is a senior radiologist with over 10 years of experience.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case is a single CT scan associated with/without the segmentation mask.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The total number of cases is 15,600. There are 15,000/100/500 cases for training, validation, and testing, respectively. Moreover, compared to the dataset in FLARE 2025, we increased 30,000 synthetic CT scans with annotated lesions. The synthetic tumor cases are from <https://huggingface.co/datasets/LWHYC/PASTA-Gen-30K>, which contains 30,000 CT scans with pixel-level lesion masks based on diffusion model [1]. Synthetic data is only used in training set. All the testing cases are from real CT scans. Participants are required to conduct ablation studies to validate the effect of using synthetic data during model training.

[1] Lei, Wenhui, et al. "A data-efficient pan-tumor foundation model for oncology ct interpretation." arXiv e-prints (2025): arXiv-2502.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

100%

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The data is provided based on the current availability with a typical split.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The data is collected according to real-world distribution.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All testing cases are unseen and unpublished.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The annotation pipeline is the same as the previous FLARE organ segmentation challenge

Ma. J, et al. Unleashing the strengths of unlabelled data in deep learning-assisted pan-cancer abdominal organ quantification: the FLARE22 challenge. *The Lancet Digital Health* 6.11 (2024): e815-e826.

Specifically, we applied a hierarchical annotation pipeline that consisted of three stages to ensure accuracy and consistency throughout the annotation process. In the first stage, an annotation consensus was formulated by a senior radiologist, an oncologist, and a surgeon based on radiation therapy oncology group consensus (RTOG) panel guideline and Netter's anatomical atlas. Specifically, the liver contour should include all hepatic parenchyma and all liver lesions. The hepatic vessels inside the liver also need to be covered. If the vessels are located outside the liver (i.e., the entrance of portal hepatitis) based on the coronal view, they should be excluded from the liver contour. The kidney contour should include the renal parenchyma while excluding adjacent structures such as blood vessels and surrounding fat.

The spleen contour should include all splenic parenchyma and any splenic lesions. It should exclude adjacent structures such as the splenic vessels (arteries and veins), particularly those located outside the spleen. The

pancreatic contour should encompass all pancreatic parenchyma including the head, body, and tail, as well as any pancreatic lesions. Exocrine, endocrine components, and the pancreatic duct need to be included, but the surrounding vessels and fat should be excluded. The aortic contour should include the entire lumen of the aorta, from the aortic root to the bifurcation. The aortic wall (including the aortic calcification) should also be included. The inferior vena cava contour should include the entire lumen and cover the walls. The adrenal gland contour should include the entire adrenal gland, both cortex and medulla, and any adrenal lesions. The gallbladder contour should encompass the entire gallbladder wall, including the body, fundus, and neck, as well as any gallstones or polyps. The cystic duct and the surrounding liver parenchyma should be excluded. The esophagus contour should include the entire esophageal wall, while adjacent structures such as the trachea, aorta, and surrounding fat and muscle should be excluded. The stomach contour should encompass the entire stomach wall including the fundus, body, antrum, and pylorus, as well as any gastric lesions. The duodenum contour should include the entire duodenal wall from the duodenal bulb to the ligament of Treitz, along with any duodenal lesions. It should exclude surrounding structures such as the head of the pancreas, common bile duct, and surrounding vasculature.

Before the annotation process, all annotators were required to learn and follow the annotation consensus.

The second stage of our annotation pipeline involved a human-in-the-loop approach aimed at enhancing annotation throughput. To facilitate this process, we utilized five 3D U-Net models trained via 5-fold cross-validation on existing abdomen CT datasets. Leveraging the predictions generated by these models, junior annotators performed manual refinements with the assistance of MedSAM on 100 randomly selected predictions, which were then checked and revised by senior radiologists. This process was iterated seven times until all the images were labeled by one of the junior annotators and further refined by the senior radiologists. In the third and final stage, we aimed to identify potential annotation errors. We trained a new set of U-Net models using five-fold cross-validation, with special attention given to images exhibiting low Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) scores (<0.75), which were then double-checked by the senior radiologists.

The experts independently drew a 3D bounding for the tumor. Then, we applied MedSAM to segment the tumors. Finally, human experts manually refined the segmentation results until they met their satisfaction.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The lesion annotations were generated by semi-automatic segmentation with MedSAM and manual correction. Annotators and radiologists were asked to use 3D Slicer software to annotate the measurable lesions based on RECIST.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

We only converted the dicom images to NifiTy format. The cases have various orientations. Participants are encouraged to develop their pre-processing methods.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Minor errors are unavoidable in medical image annotation. We will have a forum to collect feedback from participants about possible errors that they discover in the dataset.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Segmentation accuracy metrics: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) and Normalized Surface Distance (NSD).

Segmentation efficiency metrics: Runtime and GPU memory consumption (area under GPU memory-time curve).

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The metrics are complementary. Specifically, DSC and NSD are used to measure the region error and boundary error, respectively.

Running time and GPU consumption are used to measure the model efficiency.

These metrics also align with the suggestions in Metrics Reloaded.

Maier-Hein, L., Reinke, A., Godau, P. et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. Nat Methods 21, 195–212 (2024)

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

Following the recommendation in ChallengeR [1], we employ a “rank-than-aggregation” ranking scheme that includes the following three steps:

Step 1. For each testing case, we compute all metrics;

Step 2. Rank participants for each of the testing cases and each metric;

Step 3. Average all these rankings.

[1] Wiesenfarth, M., Reinke, A., Landman, B.A. et al. Methods and open-source toolkit for analyzing and visualizing challenge results. *Sci Rep* 11, 2369 (2021).

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Missing results on test cases will result in the ranks being set to the maximum (the number of teams). Specifically, missing results will get a zero value for DSC, NSD and the equivalent worst value for running time, and area under GPU memory-time curve.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The main benefit of this ranking scheme is that it can aggregate the metrics with different dimensions. A similar ranking scheme was also employed in the MICCAI BraTS Challenge 2017-2025 and FLARE 2021-2025.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

The testing cases with missing results will be assigned the worst performance. Thus, there is no missing data for the results analysis. Ranking variability will be characterized using the bootstrap.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

The Bootstrap is a simple nonparametric method that relies on minimal assumptions.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

SD across test cases and IQR will be computed to show the variability.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Ranking variability will be characterized using the bootstrap, which has been implemented in challengeR.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Wilcoxon signed rank test was used to compare the performance of different algorithms. Results were considered statistically significant if the p-value is less than 0.05.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

The testing cases with missing results will be assigned the worst performance. Thus, there is no missing data for the results analysis.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

ChallengeR

Wiesenfarth, M., Reinke, A., Landman, B.A. et al. Methods and open-source toolkit for analyzing and visualizing challenge results. Sci Rep 11, 2369 (2021).

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We will assess the performance of the ensembles of top teams.

TASK 2: Task 2: Self-configured Model for Joint 3D Medical Image Segmentation and Classification

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Deep learning models for 3D medical imaging have traditionally been handcrafted for individual tasks, either segmentation or classification, requiring extensive manual tuning of architectures, hyperparameters, and preprocessing pipelines. As clinical datasets grow in scale and complexity, this manual design process becomes increasingly inefficient and limits the deployment of adaptable, general-purpose models. Motivated by the success of the Medical Segmentation Decathlon challenge and nnU-Net (the winning solution), Task 2 focuses on building self-configured models capable of automatically adapting to diverse 3D medical imaging datasets while simultaneously performing both segmentation and classification.

This task aims to advance the next generation of autonomous model design systems for 3D medical imaging. Participants are required to design models that can automatically infer optimal configurations (e.g., architecture, resolution, patch size, normalization strategy, and loss balancing) and jointly learn high quality segmentation masks and clinically meaningful classification labels. These models should generalize across imaging modality, tumor types without task-specific manual engineering, including prostate cancer recurrence prediction in MRI scans, lung nodule diagnosis in CT scans, and liver metastasis origin prediction in PET/CT scans.

Our challenge task has four main features:

- Multi-task Learning: Models must perform both 3D segmentation and classification from the same input volume, optimizing for accuracy in both outputs while maintaining computational efficiency.
- SelfConfiguration: Solutions should include automated configuration mechanisms capable of adapting to dataset properties, such as voxel spacing, image size, contrast variability, and class imbalance, without human-designed heuristics.
- Dataset Diversity: The benchmark includes heterogeneous 3D medical imaging scans with varying modalities (CT, MRI, and PET-CT) and classification targets, encouraging the development of truly generalizable 3D models.
- Robustness and Efficiency: Models will be evaluated on segmentation accuracy (DSC and NSD), classification performance (balanced accuracy and AUROC), and resource efficiency (runtime), highlighting their potential for real-world clinical adoption.

Clinical Value: • Task 2 targets the inefficiency of manually engineering AI pipelines for every new medical dataset or clinical question. We aim to provide "plug-and-play" AI systems that can automatically adapt to new scanners, protocols, and anatomical regions without human intervention for joint disease segmentation and classification tasks.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Selfconfigured model, Joint segmentation and classification, Automated hyperparameter tuning

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Jun Ma (University Health Network, Vector Institute)

Ching-yuan Yu (University of Toronto, University Health Network, Vector Institute)

Jian He (Nanjing Drum Tower Hospital)

Bo Wang (University of Toronto, University Health Network, Vector Institute)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Jun Ma (junma.ma@mail.utoronto.ca)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Define the clinical tasks and metrics, and verify data quality

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

CodaBench (Similar to the MICCAI FLARE 2023-2025 Challenge)

Each task will have an independent challenge platform.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your

responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

N/A

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Participants should develop fully automatic models. User interaction is allowed for curating training data (i.e. excluding some training samples).

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Only the provided challenge data is allowed to be used but publicly available pre-trained models are allowed to be used.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

We will provide certificates and souvenirs for the top-5 teams.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All results will be announced publicly.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

All participants have the opportunity to publish their methods on LNCS proceedings.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker containers

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

We will provide a validation set for participants to pre-evaluate their algorithms. The testing set has the same format as the validation set. To avoid overfitting the testing set, we only offer one submission opportunity on the testing set.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

1 April 2026 (12:00 AM EST): Launch challenge registration and release training and validation data.

15 April 2026 (12:00 AM EST): Release validation dataset and open validation submission.

1 September 2026 (12:00 AM EST): Deadline for the testing submission.

15 September 2026 (12:00 AM EST): Invite top teams to prepare presentations and participate in the MICCAI 2026 Satellite Event.

4/8 October 2026: Announce final results.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Our dataset was curated from public domains (CC-BY-NC) and global data contributors with REB permits. There is no patient information included. Thus, we do not need additional ethics approval.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)

- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Evaluation code will be made available with the training data.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Top 5 teams should make their code publicly available. The remaining teams are encouraged to make their code publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Only the organizers have access to the test case labels. We are currently looking into which companies are willing to sponsor the challenge in the form of awards and computational resources.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening

- Training
- Cross-phase

Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation, Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort will be patients with disease cancer types where the images were acquired in different centers with different manufacturers.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort is composed of patients with various diseases, which were curated from 10+ different medical centers.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Computed Tomography, Magnetic Resonance Imaging, Positron Emission Tomography

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The 3D image data will be released as compressed Nifti1Image.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No additional information regarding each patient will be released.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The dataset covers whole-body regions, including head, chest, abdomen, and pelvis

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Participants have to submit a Docker image that can segment and classify various lesions in CT, MRI, and PET-CT scans.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Hardware requirements,Runtime,Robustness

DATA SETS**Data source(s)**

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The dataset was acquired from various manufacturers, such as Siemens, GE, Philips, Toshiba, Imatron, Vital, and PHMS.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Our dataset is adapted from TCIA, MSD, KiTS, autoPET, and data contributors from collaborators and local hospitals under the license permission. Thus, the acquisition protocols are very diverse. Detailed Information can be found in the following references.

[1] Simpson A, et al. A Large Annotated Medical Image Dataset for the Development and Evaluation of Segmentation Algorithms. ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:1902.09063.

[2] Heller N, et al. The kits19 challenge data: 300 kidney tumor cases with clinical context, ct semantic segmentations, and surgical outcomes. arXiv preprint arXiv:1904.00445 (2019).

[3] Clark K, et al. The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA): maintaining and operating a public information repository. Journal of Digital Imaging 26, no. 6 (2013)

[4] Ma J, et al. Abdomenct-1k: Is abdominal organ segmentation a solved problem. IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence (2021).

[5] Grossberg A, et al. Imaging and Clinical Data Archive for Head and Neck Squamous Cell Carcinoma Patients Treated with Radiotherapy. Scientific Data 5:180173 (2018)

[6] Fedorov A, et al. DICOM reencoding of volumetrically annotated Lung Imaging Database Consortium (LIDC) nodules. Medical Physics (2020)

[7] Ma. J, et al. Unleashing the strengths of unlabelled data in deep learning-assisted pan-cancer abdominal organ quantification: the FLARE22 challenge. The Lancet Digital Health 6.11 (2024): e815-e826.

[8] Ma. J, et al. Automatic organ and pan-cancer segmentation in abdomen ct: the flare 2023 challenge. ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:2408.12534

[9] Ma. J, et al. Efficient MedSAMs: Segment Anything in Medical Images on Laptop. ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:2412.16085

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Alberta Health Services

Barretos Cancer Hospital, Barretos, Sao Paulo, Brazil

Beaumont Health System, Royal Oak, MI

BioPartners, CA

Boston Medical Center, Boston, MA

Brigham and Women's Hospital, Boston, MA

Cleveland Clinic

Cureline, Inc. team and clinical network, Brisbane, CA

Hebrew University of Jerusalem

International Institute for Molecular Oncology, Poznan

IRCAD Institute Strasbourg

Lahey Hospital & Medical Center, Burlington, MA
Ludwig Maxmilian University of Munich
M Health Fairview
M.D. Anderson Cancer Center, Houston TX
Mayo Clinic, Rochester, MN
Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center (New York, NY, USA)
National Cancer Institute, Bethesda, MD
National Institutes of Health, Bethesda MD
Polytechnique & CHUM Research Center Montral
Radboud University Medical Center of Nijmegen
Roswell Park Cancer Institute, Buffalo NY
Sheba Medical Center
St. Joseph's Hospital and Medical Center, Phoenix, AZ
Tel Aviv University
The National Institutes of Health Clinical Center(NIH)
University of California, San Francisco, CA
University of Chicago
University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, NC
University of Pittsburgh/UPMC, Pittsburgh, PA
University of Sheffield
University of Southern California
Washington University School of Medicine, St. Louis, MO
Cancer Center West China Hospital
Erasmus MC Cancer Institute, Rotterdam
Fudan University Shanghai Cancer Center
Longgang Central Hospital of Shenzhen, China
Longgang District People's Hospital
University Hospital Basel

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data annotation is overseen by the challenge clinical chair Dr. Jian He, who is a senior radiologist with over 10 years of experience.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).

- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case is a single CT/MRI/PET scan associated with the segmentation mask and disease label.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Brain cancer recurrence prediction in MRI scans: 100 patients for training, 10 patients for public validation, and 50 patients for hidden testing

Lung nodule diagnosis in CT scans: 6000 patients for training, 50 patients for public validation, and 150 patients for hidden testing

Liver metastasis origin prediction in PET/CT scans: 245 patients for training, 35 patients for public validation, and 70 patients for hidden testing

At the same time, we are reaching out to other medical centers to augment the dataset, which will be determined by March 31.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

100%

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The data is provided based on the current availability with a typical split.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The data is collected according to real-world distribution.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All testing cases are unseen and unpublished.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

5

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The lesion annotations were generated by semi-automatic segmentation with MedSAM and manual correction. Annotators and radiologists were asked to use 3D Slicer software to annotate the measurable lesions based on

RECIST. The classification labels are from clinical report.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

We only converted the dicom images to NifiTy format. The cases have various orientations. Participants are encouraged to develop their pre-processing methods.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Minor errors are unavoidable in medical image annotation. We will have a forum to collect feedback from participants about possible errors that they discover in the dataset.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Segmentation accuracy metrics: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) and Normalized Surface Distance (NSD).

Classification metrics: AUROC and balanced accuracy

Segmentation efficiency metrics: Runtime and GPU memory consumption (area under GPU memory-time curve).

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The metrics are complementary. Specifically, DSC and NSD are used to measure the region error and boundary error, respectively.

Running time and GPU consumption are used to measure the model efficiency.

These metrics also align with the suggestions in Metrics Reloaded.

Maier-Hein, L., Reinke, A., Godau, P. et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. *Nat Methods* 21, 195–212 (2024)

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

Following the recommendation in ChallengeR [1], we employ a “rank-than-aggregation” ranking scheme that includes the following three steps:

Step 1. For each testing case, we compute all metrics;

Step 2. Rank participants for each of the testing cases and each metric;

Step 3. Average all these rankings.

[1] Wiesenfarth, M., Reinke, A., Landman, B.A. et al. Methods and open-source toolkit for analyzing and visualizing challenge results. *Sci Rep* 11, 2369 (2021).

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Missing results on test cases will result in the ranks being set to the maximum (the number of teams). Specifically, missing results will get a zero value for DSC, NSD and the equivalent worst value for running time, and area under GPU memory-time curve.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The main benefit of this ranking scheme is that it can aggregate the metrics with different dimensions. A similar ranking scheme was also employed in the MICCAI BraTS Challenge 2017-2025 and FLARE 2021-2025.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

The testing cases with missing results will be assigned the worst performance. Thus, there is no missing data for the results analysis. Ranking variability will be characterized using the bootstrap.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

The Bootstrap is a simple nonparametric method that relies on minimal assumptions.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

SD across test cases and IQR will be computed to show the variability.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Ranking variability will be characterized using the bootstrap, which has been implemented in challengeR.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Wilcoxon signed rank test was used to compare the performance of different algorithms. Results were considered statistically significant if the p-value is less than 0.05.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

The testing cases with missing results will be assigned the worst performance. Thus, there is no missing data for the results analysis.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

ChallengeR

Wiesenfarth, M., Reinke, A., Landman, B.A. et al. Methods and open-source toolkit for analyzing and visualizing challenge results. *Sci Rep* 11, 2369 (2021).

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We will assess the performance of the ensembles of top teams.

TASK 3: Task 3: Multimodal Model for 2D and 3D Medical Image Parsing

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Multimodal models represent a transformative approach to unify various tasks via a general token representation. This capability is particularly valuable in medical imaging, where a wide range of imaging modalities and tasks are integral to clinical workflows. This task requires to develop multimodal models that can handle five typical tasks (classification, detection, counting, measuring, and regression) across nine image modalities (CT, MRI, PET, ultrasound, X-ray, OCT, pathology, microscopy, and endoscopy). In particular, participants should train a multimodal model capable of generalizing across the following tasks:

- Classification: Identifying specific diseases, anatomical structures, or conditions
- Detection: Locating and labeling regions of interest, such as lesions or abnormalities.
- Counting: Enumerating specific entities, such as cells, glands, and lesions.
- Measuring: Quantifying dimensions, volumes, or other clinical attributes from images.
- Regression: Predicting continuous variables, such as bone age, and disease progression

Key Features

- Task Diversity: This task requires models to perform five distinct tasks, showcasing their versatility and ability to adapt to varied clinical needs.
- Modality Integration: Models must harmonize the unique characteristics and data distributions of nine imaging modalities, ensuring consistent performance across them.
- Efficiency and Scalability: Solutions should be computationally efficient, demonstrating practical scalability for deployment in real-world clinical and research settings.

Clinical Value: Task 3 seeks to replace numerous task-specific tools with a single, unified vision-language system capable of parsing nine different imaging modalities, which supports a broad spectrum of clinical needs, including cell or gland counting in pathology, lesion detection in endoscopy, and anatomical measurements in X-rays.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Multimodal learning, Foundation model, Task versatility

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

- a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Jun Ma (University Health Network, Vector Institute)

Leo Yin (University of Toronto)

Jian He (Nanjing Drum Tower Hospital)

Yaqi Wang (Communication University of Zhejiang)

Jieyun Bai (Jinan University/The University of Auckland)

Yuanfeng Ji (Stanford)

Bo Wang (University of Toronto, University Health Network, Vector Institute)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Jun Ma (junma.ma@mail.utoronto.ca)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Define the clinical tasks and metrics, and verify data quality

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

CodaBench (Similar to the MICCAI FLARE 2023-2025 Challenge)

Each task will have an independent challenge platform.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

N/A

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Participants should develop fully automatic models. User interaction is allowed for curating training data (i.e. excluding some training samples).

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Only the provided challenge data is allowed to be used but publicly available pre-trained models are allowed to be used.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

We will provide certificates and souvenirs for the top-5 teams.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All results will be announced publicly.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

All participants have the opportunity to publish their methods on LNCS proceedings.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker containers

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

We will provide a validation set for participants to pre-evaluate their algorithms. The testing set has the same format as the validation set. To avoid overfitting the testing set, we only offer one submission opportunity on the testing set.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

1 April 2026 (12:00 AM EST): Launch challenge registration and release training and validation data.

15 April 2026 (12:00 AM EST): Release validation dataset and open validation submission.

1 September 2026 (12:00 AM EST): Deadline for the testing submission.

15 September 2026 (12:00 AM EST): Invite top teams to prepare presentations and participate in the MICCAI 2026 Satellite Event.

4/8 October 2026: Announce final results.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Our dataset was curated from public domains (CC-BY-NC) and global data contributors with REB permits. There is no patient information included. Thus, we do not need additional ethics approval.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Evaluation code will be made available with the training data.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Top 5 teams should make their code publicly available. The remaining teams are encouraged to make their code publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Only the organizers have access to the test case labels. We are currently looking into which companies are willing to sponsor the challenge in the form of awards and computational resources.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification, Detection, Modeling, Prediction, Regression

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort will be patients with disease cancer types where the images were acquired in different centers with different manufacturers.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort is composed of patients with various diseases, which were curated from 10+ different medical centers.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Computed Tomography, Magnetic Resonance Imaging, Positron Emission Tomography, ultrasound, X-ray, Optical Coherence Tomography, endoscopy, fundus, and microscopy images

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The 2D and 3D image data will be released as JPEG and compressed Nifti1Image formats, respectively. The Nifti files will include an affine matrix and header defining the rotation, origin, and spacing of each image.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No additional information regarding each patient will be released.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The dataset covers whole-body regions, including head, chest, abdomen, and pelvis

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Participants have to submit a Docker image that can conduct classification, detection, counting, measurement, and regression tasks.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Hardware requirements,Runtime,Robustness

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The dataset was acquired from various manufacturers, such as Siemens, GE, Philips, Toshiba, Imatron, Vital, and PHMS.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Our dataset is adapted from TCIA, MSD, KiTS, autoPET, and data contributors from collaborators and local hospitals under the license permission. Thus, the acquisition protocols are very diverse. Detailed Information can be found in the following references.

[1] Simpson A, et al. A Large Annotated Medical Image Dataset for the Development and Evaluation of Segmentation Algorithms. ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:1902.09063.

[2] Heller N, et al. The kits19 challenge data: 300 kidney tumor cases with clinical context, ct semantic segmentations, and surgical outcomes. arXiv preprint arXiv:1904.00445 (2019).

[3] Clark K, et al. The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA): maintaining and operating a public information repository. Journal of Digital Imaging 26, no. 6 (2013)

[4] Ma J, et al. Abdomenct-1k: Is abdominal organ segmentation a solved problem. IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence (2021).

[5] Grossberg A, et al. Imaging and Clinical Data Archive for Head and Neck Squamous Cell Carcinoma Patients Treated with Radiotherapy. Scientific Data 5:180173 (2018)

[6] Fedorov A, et al. DICOM reencoding of volumetrically annotated Lung Imaging Database Consortium (LIDC) nodules. Medical Physics (2020)

[7] Ma. J, et al. Unleashing the strengths of unlabelled data in deep learning-assisted pan-cancer abdominal organ quantification: the FLARE22 challenge. The Lancet Digital Health 6.11 (2024): e815-e826.

[8] Ma. J, et al. Automatic organ and pan-cancer segmentation in abdomen ct: the flare 2023 challenge. ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:2408.12534

[9] Ma. J, et al. Efficient MedSAMs: Segment Anything in Medical Images on Laptop. ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:2412.16085

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Alberta Health Services

Barretos Cancer Hospital, Barretos, Sao Paulo, Brazil

Beaumont Health System, Royal Oak, MI

BioPartners, CA

Boston Medical Center, Boston, MA

Brigham and Women's Hospital, Boston, MA

Cleveland Clinic

Cureline, Inc. team and clinical network, Brisbane, CA

Hebrew University of Jerusalem

International Institute for Molecular Oncology, Poznan

IRCAD Institute Strasbourg

Lahey Hospital & Medical Center, Burlington, MA
Ludwig Maxmilian University of Munich
M Health Fairview
M.D. Anderson Cancer Center, Houston TX
Mayo Clinic, Rochester, MN
Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center (New York, NY, USA)
National Cancer Institute, Bethesda, MD
National Institutes of Health, Bethesda MD
Polytechnique & CHUM Research Center Montral
Radboud University Medical Center of Nijmegen
Roswell Park Cancer Institute, Buffalo NY
Sheba Medical Center
St. Joseph's Hospital and Medical Center, Phoenix, AZ
Tel Aviv University
The National Institutes of Health Clinical Center(NIH)
University of California, San Francisco, CA
University of Chicago
University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, NC
University of Pittsburgh/UPMC, Pittsburgh, PA
University of Sheffield
University of Southern California
Washington University School of Medicine, St. Louis, MO
Cancer Center West China Hospital
Erasmus MC Cancer Institute, Rotterdam
Fudan University Shanghai Cancer Center
Longgang Central Hospital of Shenzhen, China
Longgang District People's Hospital
University Hospital Basel

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data annotation is overseen by the challenge clinical chair Dr. Jian He, who is a senior radiologist with over 10 years of experience.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).

- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case is a single CT/MR/PET scan or an ultrasound, X-ray, Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT), endoscopy, fundus, and microscopy image

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Training set (lesion detection and measurement in various disease): CT: 10,000; MRI (lesion detection and measurement in various abdominal cancer types): 10,000; Microscopy: 1000; Ultrasound: 700; X-ray (permanent teeth detection in panoramic X-ray images): 1000; OCT: 100; Pathology (glomeruli counting and detection in various chronic kidney diseases): 1000; Endoscopy Images (polyp detection): 1000

Validation set: CT: 100; MRI: 100; Microscopy: 100; Ultrasound: 100; X-ray: 100; OCT: 10; Pathology: 100;

Endoscopy Images: 50

Testing set: CT: 300, MRI: 300; Microscopy: 400; Ultrasound: 200; X-ray: 200; OCT: 50; Pathology: 200; Endoscopy Images: 100

All training cases have prompts and the associated answer. In addition to the images, we provide a well-structured json file to specify Task Type, Modality, Input Image Name, Question, and Answer. The minor wording issue is also fixed.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

100%

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The data is provided based on the current availability with a typical split.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The data is collected according to real-world distribution.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All testing cases are unseen and unpublished.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

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b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The disease labels are obtained from radiology reports or pathological examinations. Other detection and counting labels are obtained by manual annotations.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

We only converted the dicom images to NifiTy format. The cases have various orientations. Participants are encouraged to develop their pre-processing methods.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Minor errors are unavoidable in medical image annotation. We will have a forum to collect feedback from participants about possible errors that they discover in the dataset.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Classification tasks: AUROC and balanced accuracy

Detection tasks: FROC score

Counting and measurement task: Mean Absolute Error

Efficiency metrics: Runtime and GPU memory consumption (area under GPU memory-time curve).

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The accuracy metrics are selected based on the recommendation in Metrics Reloaded.

Maier-Hein, L., Reinke, A., Godau, P. et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. *Nat Methods* 21, 195–212 (2024).

Running time and GPU consumption are used to measure the model efficiency.

These metrics also align with the suggestions in Metrics Reloaded.

Maier-Hein, L., Reinke, A., Godau, P. et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. *Nat Methods* 21, 195–212 (2024)

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

Following the recommendation in ChallengeR [1], we employ a “rank-than-aggregation” ranking scheme that includes the following three steps:

Step 1. For each testing case, we compute all metrics;

Step 2. Rank participants for each of the testing cases and each metric;

Step 3. Average all these rankings.

[1] Wiesenfarth, M., Reinke, A., Landman, B.A. et al. Methods and open-source toolkit for analyzing and visualizing challenge results. *Sci Rep* 11, 2369 (2021).

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Missing results on test cases will result in the ranks being set to the maximum (the number of teams). Specifically, missing results will get a zero value for DSC, NSD and the equivalent worst value for running time, and area under GPU memory-time curve.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The main benefit of this ranking scheme is that it can aggregate the metrics with different dimensions. A similar ranking scheme was also employed in the MICCAI BraTS Challenge 2017-2025 and FLARE 2021-2025.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

The testing cases with missing results will be assigned the worst performance. Thus, there is no missing data for the results analysis. Ranking variability will be characterized using the bootstrap.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

The Bootstrap is a simple nonparametric method that relies on minimal assumptions.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

SD across test cases and IQR will be computed to show the variability.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Ranking variability will be characterized using the bootstrap, which has been implemented in challengeR.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Wilcoxon signed rank test was used to compare the performance of different algorithms. Results were considered statistically significant if the p-value is less than 0.05.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

The testing cases with missing results will be assigned the worst performance. Thus, there is no missing data for the results analysis.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

ChallengeR

Wiesenfarth, M., Reinke, A., Landman, B.A. et al. Methods and open-source toolkit for analyzing and visualizing challenge results. Sci Rep 11, 2369 (2021).

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We will assess the performance of the ensembles of top teams.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

N/A

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A